

The Influence of Advertising Appeal and Sales Promotion on Purchasing Decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang

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ABSTRACT: This study analyzes the effect of advertising appeal and sales promotion on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang. A quantitative approach was used with data collected from 100 respondents through an offline questionnaire using purposive sampling. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression and hypothesis testing. Descriptive results show that respondents generally agree or strongly agree with the statements proposed. The classical assumption test shows that the data meets the requirements of normality, no multicollinearity, and no heteroscedasticity. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.83 indicates that 83% of the variation in purchasing decisions can be explained by the independent variables, while 17% is influenced by other factors. The t-test shows that advertising appeal ($t = 8.505$, sig. 0.000) and sales promotion ($t = 9.501$, sig. 0.000) have a significant effect partially. The F test shows a significant effect simultaneously ($F = 236.716$, sig. 0.000). This study concludes that enhancing advertising appeal and applying varied sales promotion strategies can significantly increase purchasing decisions. The findings provide practical recommendations for improving the marketing strategy at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif.

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INTRODUCTION

In the era of digitalization, the education technology (EduTech) sector becomes a key industry that plays a significant role in improving education and developing human resources. The growth of technology and the high internet penetration rate in Indonesia encourage many companies to innovate and provide educational services through online platforms. This phenomenon results in a dramatic rise in the number of EduTech companies in Indonesia, reflecting the large potential for education supported by technology. However, the competition in this industry becomes increasingly tight, prompting companies to find effective strategies to attract consumers and influence their purchasing decisions.

Previous studies show the role of advertising appeal and sales promotion in affecting purchase decisions. A study by Suheri et al. (2022) shows that the appeal of advertisements has a significant and strong influence on purchasing decisions. Ikawati et al. (2021) also find that advertising appeal positively and significantly affects consumers' decisions to buy a product. Furthermore, Subagiyo et al. (2022) and Santoso and Rosyidi (2024) state that sales promotions, through incentives and special offers, positively influence buying decisions by making products more desirable and accessible to consumers.

Despite this, the findings of previous studies are not entirely consistent. Some research, such as Elsyana et al. (2022), finds that while the appeal of advertisements has a positive influence, it does not significantly affect purchasing decisions. In addition, there is a phenomenon of declining sales at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang in November and December 2024, even though the company applies strategies to promote their products through attractive advertisements and promotions. The main issue may lie in the delivery and creativity of the promotions, which may be less effective in influencing consumers' buying decisions.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the influence of advertising appeal and sales promotion on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang. Specifically, it seeks to (1) identify the partial effect of advertisement appeal on purchasing

decisions; (2) identify the partial effect of sales promotion on purchasing decisions; and (3) identify the simultaneous effects of advertisement appeal and sales promotion on purchasing decisions.

This research contributes to both theory and practice. Theoretically, it adds to the body of knowledge by examining the roles of advertisement appeal and promotions in influencing purchasing decisions within the context of an EduTech company. Practically, the results provide useful insights for companies, especially PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang, to develop more effective strategies to attract consumers and drive sales, thereby strengthening their competitiveness in the digital education industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW Marketing

Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 27) "marketing is meeting needs profitability" means that marketing is an activity carried out by an organization or institution to meet consumer needs in a way that benefits all parties involved. Another opinion is also expressed by Indrasari (2019: 2), namely marketing is a comprehensive, integrated, and planned activity, carried out by an organization in doing business in order to be able to accommodate market demand by creating products of selling value, determining prices, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offers of value to users, clients, partners, and the general public.

Marketing Management

Kotler & Keller (2016: 27), marketing management is the art and science of selecting target markets and reaching, retaining, and growing customers by creating, delivering, and communicating superior customer value. Meanwhile, according to Indrasari (2019: 8) marketing management is a series of processes for analyzing, planning, implementing, and monitoring and controlling a marketing activity where the aim is to achieve company targets effectively and efficiently.

Purchase Decisions

The purchasing decision was defined by Kotler and Armstrong (2015) as the behavior of individuals or organizations in selecting, buying, and using products or services to fulfill their needs. The decision-making process involved several stages, namely need recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision, and post-purchase evaluation. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2015:227) there are six indicators of purchase decision, namely: 1. Product Choice, 2. Brand Choice, 3. Dealer Choice, 4. Purchase Amount, 5. Purchase Timing, 6. Payment Method.

Ads Appeal

According to Amandeep et al. (2017), advertising appeal referred to the components used in advertisements to attract the audience's attention and influence them to become interested in the advertised product or service. Amandeep et al. (2017) also stated that there were five indicators of advertising appeal, namely: 1. Interest When Watching The Advertisement, 2. Uniqueness Of The Advertisement, 3. Informativeness Of The Advertisement, 4. Clarity Of The Advertisement, 5. Desire To Purchase The Advertised Product

Sales Promotion

Personal Kotler and Keller (2016) explained that sales promotion consisted of various short-term incentive tactics intended to encourage customers or businesses to purchase certain goods or services more quickly. Kotler and Keller emphasized that this promotion had to be part of a broader marketing strategy and had to be used strategically so that it did not reduce the brand's value in the eyes of consumers. Kotler and Keller (2016:520) also stated that there were five indicators of sales promotion, namely: 1. Trial, 2. Coupons, 3. Rebates (Discount), 4. Price Packs, 5. Premiums.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study was conducted at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang to examine the influence of advertising appeal and sales promotion on consumer purchasing decisions. The research involved three variables: purchasing decision as the dependent variable (Y), and advertising appeal (X1) and sales promotion (X2) as independent variables. A total of 100 respondents were selected using purposive sampling, with criteria including having purchased products from PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif between September and December 2024, following the Instagram accounts of KarirCPNS, KarirBUMN, or KarirPTN, and having seen advertisements from PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif.

This study employed a quantitative approach using primary data collected through offline questionnaires. Measurement instruments were based on indicators from Kotler and Armstrong for purchasing decisions, Amandeep et al. (2017) for advertising appeal, and Kotler & Keller (2016) for sales promotion. The analysis included validity and reliability testing, descriptive statistics, classical assumption tests (normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity), multiple linear regression, and hypothesis testing using t-test and F-test. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was also calculated to determine how much of the variation in purchasing decisions was explained by the independent variables.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 Ads Appeal Validity Test Results

Variable	Item	r hitting	r table	Sig	α	Hasil
Ads Appeal (X1)	X1.1.1	0,827	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.1.2	0,727	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.1.3	0,875	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2.1	0,792	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2.2	0,771	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2.3	0,828	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.3.1	0,825	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.3.2	0,790	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.1	0,865	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.2	0,859	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.3	0,894	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.1	0,874	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.2	0,825	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.3	0,864	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid

Table 2 Sales Promotion Validity Test Results

Personal Selling (X2)	X2.1.1	0,847	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.1.2	0,830	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.2.1	0,849	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.2.2	0,809	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.1	0,745	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.2	0,826	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.3	0,704	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.4.1	0,783	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.4.2	0,702	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.5.1	0,809	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.5.2	0,822	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid

Table 3 Purchase Decision Validity Test Results

Personal Selling (X2)	Y1.1.1	0,779	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.1.2	0,780	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.2.1	0,693	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.2.2	0,793	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3.1	0,739	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3.2	0,765	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3.3	0,769	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.4.1	0,783	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.4.2	0,773	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.5.1	0,805	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.5.2	0,744	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.6.1	0,779	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.6.2	0,747	0,196	0,000	0,05	Valid

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on field observations of 100 respondents who evaluated advertising appeal and sales promotion on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang, the research instrument was tested in advance using the SPSS Statistics 26 application. The results of the validity test showed that all statement items used to measure the variables of advertising appeal (X1), sales promotion (X2), and purchasing decisions (Y) were declared valid. This was proven by the fact that the calculated r-values for each statement item were greater than the r-table value (0.1966) at a significance level of < 0.05.

Thus, all statement items for the variables of advertising appeal (X1), sales promotion (X2), and purchasing decisions (Y) were suitable for

measuring the effect of each variable on the purchasing decisions of products at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang. The validity of this instrument served as an important foundation to ensure that the collected data accurately represented the real influence of the company's marketing strategies on consumer behavior.

Table 4 Reliability Test Results

Reliability Test			
Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Standar	Information
Ads Appeal (X1)	0,965	0,60	Reliabel
Sales Promotion (X2)	0,941	0,60	Reliabel
Purchase Decisions (Y)	0,940	0,60	Reliabel

Based on Table 4, the reliability test results showed that all variables had a Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.60. This indicated that the items of the advertising appeal variable (X1), sales promotion (X2), and purchasing decision (Y) were considered reliable and trustworthy as measurement instruments in this study.

Figure 1 Normality Test Results

Based on the results of the normality test using the normality probability plot, the influence of advertising appeal and sales promotion on purchasing decisions was in accordance with the basis for decision-making in the normality test. If the data spread around the diagonal line and followed the direction of the diagonal line, or if the histogram showed a normal distribution pattern, then the results of the normality test for this regression model were declared to meet the normality assumption.

Table 5 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinerarity		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
Ads Appeal (X1)	0,568	1,761	No Multicollinearity Occurs
Sales Promotion (X2)	0,568	1,761	No Multicollinearity Occurs

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on Table 5 above, the multicollinearity test results can be seen that the VIF value of the ads appeal and sales promotion variables has a tolerance > 0.10 and VIF < 10, thus the independent variables can be said to have no multicollinearity.

Figure 2 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Based on Figure 2, the results of the heteroscedasticity test can be seen that the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, it can be concluded that this regression model does not occur heteroscedasticity.

Table 6 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Coefficients ^a							Collinearity	
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	1,421	2.134		.666	.507		
	Price Perception	0,412	.048	.473	8.505	.000	0,568	1.709
	Personal Selling	0,604	.064	.528	9.501	.000	0,568	1.709
a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decisions								

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis test in the table above, a multiple linear regression model equation can be seen as follows :

$$Y = 1,421 + 0,412 X_1 + 0,604 X_2 + e$$

The multiple linear regression equation shows the direction of influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The explanation of the multiple linear regression equation is as follows :

1. The constant value (a) was 1.421, meaning that if all independent variables, namely advertising appeal (X1) and sales promotion (X2), were assumed to be zero, then the purchasing decision variable (Y) would be 1.421.
2. The regression coefficient of the advertising appeal variable (b1) was 0.412 and had a positive value. This meant that if there was an increase of one unit in the advertising appeal variable while the sales promotion variable was assumed to be zero, then the purchasing decision (Y) would increase by 0.412.
3. The regression coefficient of the sales promotion variable (b2) was 0.604 and also had a positive value. This meant that if there was an increase of one unit in the sales promotion variable while the advertising appeal variable was assumed to be zero, then the purchasing decision (Y) would increase by 0.604.

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis, the variables advertising appeal (X1) and sales promotion (X2) that had the greatest contribution or influence on purchasing decisions (Y) was sales promotion (X2) with a coefficient of 0.604, compared to advertising appeal (X1) with a coefficient of 0.412.

Table 7 Coefficient of Determination Analysis Results

Model	Adjusted (R ²)
1	0,826

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on Table 4.15, the results of the analysis of the coefficient of determination (R^2) showed that the Adjusted R Square value obtained

was 0.826. This value indicated that the contribution of the influence of advertising appeal and sales promotion on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang was 82.6%, while the remaining 17.4% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Table 8 Partial Hypothesis Test Results

Variabel	t_{hitung}	t_{tabel}	Significant	Tingkat Signifikan (α)	Information
Ads Appeal	8,505	1,984	0,000	0,05	Significant
Salss Promotion	9.501	1,984	0,000	0,05	Significant

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on table 8, partial hypothesis testing above, it can be concluded that:

1. H_a for Hypothesis 1 was accepted and H_0 was rejected. This was because the advertising appeal variable had a t-count $>$ t-table, namely $8.505 > 1.984$, and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it was concluded that Hypothesis (H_1), which stated that advertising appeal partially had a positive effect on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang, was accepted.
2. H_a for Hypothesis 2 was accepted and H_0 was rejected. This was because the sales promotion variable had a t-count $>$ t-table, namely $9.501 > 1.984$, and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it was concluded that Hypothesis (H_2), which stated that sales promotion partially had a positive effect on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang, was accepted.

Table 9 Simultaneous Hypothesis Test Results

F_{hitung}	F_{tabel}	Signifikan	Tingkat Signifikan	Information
236, 716	3,090	0,000	0,05	Significant

Based on Table 4.17, the results of the simultaneous hypothesis testing (F-test) showed that H_a for Hypothesis 3 was accepted and H_0 was rejected. This was because the F_{count} was greater than the F_{table} , namely $236.716 > 3.090$, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Based on these criteria, it was concluded that Hypothesis (H_3), which stated that advertising appeal and sales promotion simultaneously had a positive effect on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang, was accepted.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the research analysis conducted the following discussion can be made :

1. The Influence of Ads Appeal on the Purchase Decisions

Based on the descriptive analysis of the advertising appeal variable, the "informative advertisement" indicator had the highest mean score of 3.80. This indicates that the majority of respondents strongly agreed that PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang was able to deliver clear and useful information through advertisements, such as customer reviews, product explanations, or usage tutorials. This shows that the advertisements created were not only visually appealing but also provided a strong understanding of the products or services offered.

The results of the partial hypothesis testing showed that advertising appeal had a positive effect on purchasing decisions. This was evidenced by the t-test result, where $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($8.505 > 1.984$) and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This finding supports the hypothesis that advertising appeal positively influenced purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang. The highest scoring item within the variable was "advertisements provide clear information," with a mean score of 3.98, categorized as high. This indicates that PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif was able to convey clear and relevant information regarding product benefits, features, and advantages—such as those of karircpn.id, karirppk.id, karirbumn.net, and karirptn.id—thus attracting the attention of potential users and shaping positive perceptions toward the services.

Most users came from a young demographic aged 21–30, including final-year students, fresh graduates, and private employees seeking to shift their careers into civil service or BUMN sectors. These characteristics reflect a demand for fast, flexible, and practical digital-based career education and training. Through informative and targeted advertising, PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif effectively reached this segment. Potential users felt supported in their decision-making process because the ads delivered relevant, easily accessible, and need-based information for their career development.

This finding supports the results of previous research by Suheri et al. (2022), titled The Influence of Advertising Appeal and Brand Image on Purchase Intention and Its Impact on Purchase Decision (Case Study on Sriwijaya Air), which stated that advertising

appeal has a strong and positive effect on purchasing decisions. Based on all the data obtained, it can be concluded that advertising appeal had a positive effect on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang.

2. The Influence of Personal Selling on the Purchase Decisions

Based on the descriptive analysis of the sales promotion variable, the “trial” indicator had the highest mean score of 3.72. This shows that respondents agreed with the promotional approach of providing trials, such as free access to test new packages and preview questions before purchase. Respondents felt that PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif made it easier for potential users to try out initial access to the *karircpns.id* and *karirbumn.net* platforms before deciding to use paid services.

The partial hypothesis testing results showed that sales promotion had a positive influence on the use of digital services. This was evidenced by the t-test value ($t_{count} = 9.501 > t_{table} = 1.984$) and significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. This finding confirmed the hypothesis stating that sales promotion positively influenced purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang.

In the sales promotion variable, the highest mean score came from the “new product offer” indicator, which scored 4.01—classified as high. The strategy of offering free trials or limited access to features on platforms such as *karircpns.id* and *karirbumn.net* was perceived as effective in building user trust, especially among students, fresh graduates, and job seekers aged 21–30 years. This age group tends to verify service quality before committing to purchases or subscriptions. Thus, offering digital samples served as a relevant promotional strategy that encouraged purchasing or service usage decisions.

These results support the findings of Pusporini et al. (2023) in their research titled *The Influence of Dompnet Digital, Sales Promotion, and Service Quality on Consumer Purchase Decisions at Indomaret (Case Study in South Jakarta)*, which concluded that sales promotion significantly affected purchasing decisions. Therefore, it can be stated that sales promotion had a positive influence on the use of digital services at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang.

3. The Influence of Ads Appeal and Sales Promotion on the Purchase Decisions

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination analysis, the Adjusted R Square was 0.826 or 82.6%. This indicates that the combined contribution of advertising appeal and sales promotion to purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang was 82.6%, while the remaining 17.4% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

The multiple linear regression analysis showed that sales promotion had the greatest contribution to purchasing decisions, with a coefficient of 0.604, compared to advertising appeal, which had a coefficient of 0.412. This suggests that the role of sales promotion at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif played a more dominant part in influencing consumer decisions.

The simultaneous hypothesis test also supported these findings, as F_{count} was greater than F_{table} ($236.716 > 3.090$) and the significance value was $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it was concluded that advertising appeal and sales promotion simultaneously had a positive effect on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Malang.

RESEARCH CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, the research results can be concluded as follows:

1. Advertising appeal has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions at PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang, with a regression coefficient value of 0.412. Aspects such as interest when watching the advertisement, uniqueness, informativeness, message clarity, and the desire to purchase play an important role in influencing consumer purchasing decisions.
2. Sales promotion also has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, with a regression coefficient of 0.604. Promotional strategies such as offering trials, coupons, discounts, digital gifts, and price packs contribute more than advertising appeal, making them a main focus in marketing strategy.
3. Advertising appeal and sales promotion simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, with an Adjusted R Square value of 0.826. This means that 82.6% of the variation in purchasing decisions is influenced by these two variables, while the remaining 17.4% is affected by other factors not examined in this study.

Suggestions

Based on the conclusions obtained, the suggestions that can be conveyed are : Suggestions for PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang

1) Advertising Appeal

The company needs to optimize advertising videos by using music that captures consumers’ attention, visuals that match the product theme, and engaging animations or delivery styles to more effectively increase consumer interest from the first second of viewing.

2) Sales Promotion

The company is advised to enhance its price pack/cent-off deal strategies by offering economical price packages and special pricing through more attractive product bundling tailored to consumer needs.

- 3) The company is recommended to improve the uniqueness and advantages of its products compared to other alternatives available in the market, so that consumers feel more confident in choosing PT Alfath Teknologi Kreatif Kota Malang as their primary option.

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